

Tara Tumbongan Tayo: An assessment of food safety and sanitation practices in selected tumbongan food stalls in Manila

John Christian Espinola, Ell Clifferson C. Gallardo, Elijah Manalo, Bryle Tucpi, Euonna Tagle, Yzabeil Carnites, Giordan Geminiano, Kier Pajarillo, Paolo Reyes, Patricia Manlusoc, Paulo Atienza, Precious Santos

Abstract

Four hundred and three (403) randomly selected customers in Manila answered the survey instrument by Pivarnik et al. (2012) which includes assessment indicators on cooking preparations, cleanliness and hygiene, receiving and service, allergens, and establishment conditions. Results show that customers find concrete evidence that food may easily be taken to go (78.2%) and are in containers that are observable, clean, and new (73.2%); food is adequately cooked (73.4%); and food served looks appetizing and has no foul odor (73.2%). Laboratory tests using FDA BAM – 4 2020 (MPN Method) on three (3) samples of *Tumbong* Soup was conducted and all revealed less than 3 (<3.0) counts of e-coli showing a very low-level risk of contamination. This can increase confidence of customers, enhance reputation and continuity of the establishment, solidification of regulatory compliance and quality assurance. As the researcher's expertise lies in anything food-related or within the culinary field, the researchers chose this topic to further analyze the food safety and sanitation practices of selected *tumbongan* stalls and to determine the safety of consuming *tumbong* soup, which is made from pig's rectum—a waste product.

Keywords: Food safety and sanitation; Food microorganism; Street food.

John Christian Espinola*

Lyceum of the Philippines University, Manila, Philippines

E-mail: christian.espinola@lpu.edu.ph

Ell Clifferson C. Gallardo

Lyceum of the Philippines University, Manila, Philippines

E-mail: ell.gallardo@lpunetwork.edu.ph

Elijah Manalo

Bryle Tucpi

Euonna Tagle

Yzabeil Carnites

Giordan Geminiano

Kier Pajarillo

Paolo Reyes

Patricia Manlusoc

Paulo Atienza

Precious Santos

Lyceum of the Philippines University, Manila, Philippines

*Corresponding author

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Introduction

Filipino street food is a blend of flavors representing the nation's rich culinary legacy, ranging from classic skewers cooked over charcoal to tiny, deep-fried treats. Due to centuries of gastronomic advancements and cultural influences, Filipino street food has undergone an interesting evolution (Austria, 2024). *Tumbong* soup or Pork Bung Soup, a famous cuisine served along the busy street food hubs, is a broth produced from the large intestines of cows or pigs, although eating entrails may seem a bit extreme, locals and food enthusiasts alike adore the soup's warm, meaty flavor. The researchers intend to achieve the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal numbers 3.3 and 2.1, namely, "Good health and well-being—Infectious diseases" and "Zero Hunger—Universal access to safe and nutritious food"—by studying topics on food safety, sanitation, and hygienic practices (Our World in Data, 2023; World Health Organization, n.d.). Moreover, the promotion of safety and building resilience to secure the public health is another objective of this study which falls under the goals of *Ambisyon Natin 2040*. This paper hopes to promote cleanliness and sanitary practices on the process of preparation and service of street foods not only by assessing consumer perception on the food establishment's current sanitary practices but also scientifically through experimental means. According to Lubos (2014) the poor food preparation and sanitary practices of Filipino street vendors is one of the many prevalent issues in the context of food safety. The Food Safety Act of 2013 also known as Republic Act no. 10611, was created to guarantee food safety, quality, and hygiene through a regulatory system managed by the Food Safety Regulatory Coordinating Board (FSRCB) to ensure the standards among food chains as a means of protecting the public health and gain consumers' trust. This research aims to analyze the demographic profiles of the customer respondents, evaluate safety and sanitation practices of the selected food stalls, and determine if there is a presence of *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) in soup samples from selected *tumbongan* food stalls in Manila. The study will focus on microbiological contamination caused by *Escherichia coli*, specifically the STEC (Shiga Toxin *Escherichia Coli*), which is commonly found in intestines of both humans and animals and may cause fatal infections when contracted (New York State Department of Health, 2023).

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive experimental research design was used in this study. Within the selected tumbongan food stalls, the descriptive component of the research design aims to give a thorough description of the present condition of food safety and sanitation procedures. According to Bell (2009), using the experimental design, the researchers may monitor factors on variables and clear up any ambiguity that influences food safety and sanitation outcomes. In addition, it modifies various factors to determine the most important results.

Research Locale

The study is conducted at food stalls along a selected street in Tondo, Manila, Philippines. To ensure data privacy the researchers will be using codes to identify the chosen locales. The *tumbongan* food stalls are coded as *Tumbongan* stall A, *Tumbongan* stall B, and *Tumbongan* stall C. The location was chosen because it is a microcosm of the neighborhood street food market and makes it possible to conduct a targeted evaluation of the hygiene and food safety sanitation practices in this neighborhood. The area is densely populated, and the food stalls play a crucial role in providing affordable meals to residents.

Sampling Design

Respondents would be gathered through purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling is prone to researcher subjectivity because the researcher handpicks participants who possess specific characteristics that align with their expertise or knowledge, which can lead to biased results.

A sample of 403 respondents would be selected from the population of 15 years old and above *Tumbong* soup consumers from the three (3) *Tumbongan* stalls that the researchers picked. At the 95% confidence level, a margin error of +/- 5% is provided by 403 survey respondents. This meant that, for every 100 respondents to a survey, 95 times out of 100 times the results would range between +5% and -5% of the totals that were published.

Instrumentation

The study used closed-ended survey questionnaires written in English to conduct the surveys in selected *Tumbongan* food stalls in Manila. The researchers adapted the survey instrument from the study entitled "*Assessment of Food Safety Knowledge and Attitudes of Managers of Residential Childcare Institutions (RCCI) in the Northeast*" (Pivarnik et al., 2012). The questionnaire, validated by experts, consists of 43 items divided into five (5) parts: Cooking / Preparation, Receiving Service, Cleanliness / Hygiene, Establishment Condition, and Allergens. The respondents answered the survey using three (3) Likert scales which are: Evident, Not Evident, and No Sufficient Evidence. The survey also included the demographic profile of the respondents which are: sex, age, highest educational background (post graduate), employment status, knowledge on food safety, average amount spent on Manila, frequency of eating out in Manila, residence, accompanied visits, food allergens, preference on dietary restrictions, and frequency of eating *tumbong* soup.

Data Gathering Procedure

Copies of the survey were distributed to the chosen respondents. The researchers verbally provided the instructions for the survey questionnaire and asked for the respondent's consent to participate by signing in the consent form located on the back page. All parts of the survey were answered by the respondents, including the consent form on the last page. The data gathered from this study were then tallied and analyzed for further interpretation. For the sole purpose of conducting the study, the researchers ensured that the respondents' identities would be kept confidential.

Statistical Treatment

Frequency distribution is used for the study; it is an organized table that shows the number of individuals in each category in a scale of measurement (Manikandan, 2011). FDA BAM - 4 2020 (MPN Method) is also used in the study for the laboratory testing to determine if the samples of soup collected to selected *Tumbongan* stalls contain *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*). According to United States Food and Drug Administration (2024), FDA BAM method is the most preferred laboratory testing for microbiological analysis on food samples.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents (n = 403)

Variables	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Female	226	56.1%
	Male	172	42.7%
	Prefer not to say	5	1.2%
Age	Below 25	275	68.2%
	26-35	106	26.3%
	36 above	22	5.5%
Employment	Employed	186	46.2%
	Unemployed	30	7.4%
	Self-Employed	187	46.4%
Highest Educational Attainment	Basic Education	96	23.8%
	Tertiary	199	49.4%
	Non-Formal	10	2.5%
	Postgraduate	98	24.3%
Amount Spent on Food Transaction	Less than Php 500	217	53.8%
	Php 500-Php 1000	141	35%
	More than Php 1000	45	11.2%
Frequency of Eating Out in Manila	First time	147	36.5%
	Second time	72	17.9%
	More than 2 times	184	45.7%
Accompanied Visits	Solo	10	2.5%
	Friends	245	60.8%
	Family	134	33.3%
	Workmates	14	3.5%
Food Allergens	Yes	41	10.2%
	No	362	89.8%
Encountered Discomfort That Required Medical Assistance While Eating in Food Hubs	Yes	16	4%
	No	387	96%
Preference on Dietary Restrictions	Yes	9	2.2%
	No	394	97.8%
Frequency in Eating <i>Tumbong</i> Soup in Manila	First time	225	55.8%
	Second time	64	15.9%
	More than 2 times	114	28.3%

A survey about the frequency of eating out in Manila was handed out that reached the total of 403 respondents. The research findings provide several key insights about the preferences and behaviors of consumers regarding food stalls, particularly *Tumbongan* stalls. A frequency of 126 (56.1%) female respondents are likely to eat in *Tumbongan* stalls. since they provide easy access to food and are close to dormitories. Individuals ages 25 and below consisting of 275 individuals (68%) are the most common customers, mostly students. Having a frequency of 187 (46.6), individuals who are employed and are busy due to hectic schedules visit *Tumbongan* stalls due to convenience within time since they do not have time to cook (Sasson, n.d). Customers with the highest educational attainment are tertiary graduates with over 199 (49.4%) respondents. Price and convenience have been major factors affecting the individual's decisions because of their affordability and ease of access, especially if they are near their university and workplace (Kenton, 2021). For the average amount spent on food by 217 (53.8) individuals is less than Php 500, as their average expenses on street foods are due to most Filipinos socioeconomic backgrounds in their dining habits (Mendoza, 2022). Repeat customers who ate more than twice in the food stalls in Manila are 184 (45.7%) individuals. The study of Sharif et al. (2017) stated that individuals have incorporated dining out in their lifestyle especially in social context and many choose to dine out for a change of pace and to eat delicious meals. These individuals may also develop a preference for a certain place or establishment which supports the results showing that most of the respondents tend to eat out and return to Manila more than two times. While the frequency of people in Manila eating *Tumbong* soup acquired a number of 225 (55.8%) people who visits *Tumbongan* stalls mostly are first timers, second is the individuals who ate *Tumbong* soup more than three times gathering a result of 114 (28.3%) individuals, and last are the persons who tried *Tumbong* soup for the second time with the sum of 64 (15.9%) people. For the individuals who visited and ate at Manila with companions collected a total of 245 (60.8%) respondents who dined with their friends who are first in the group, second in the group is the individuals with their family gathering the total of 134 (33.3%) family members, and last are 10 (2.5%) individuals who ate unaccompanied. Also, Individuals who had preference on dietary restrictions was asked to answer the survey, obtaining nine individuals (2.2%) who had dietary restrictions and 394 (97.8%) respondents answered no. Food allergens was also examined, collecting the number of foodies who answered no was 362 (89.8%) foodies, and people who answered yes had the amount of 41 (10.2%) foodies. These food allergens include seafood, crustacean, shellfish, nuts, and chicken. Individuals who encountered discomfort that required medical assistance gathered 394 (97.8%) respondents who answered no, and 16 people (4%) answered yes.

Assessment on Food Safety and Sanitation Practices

Hereby are the respondent's assessment on evident food safety and sanitation practices. 315 or 78.2% of respondents state that foods may be taken to go. Moreover, respondents stated that the food is adequately cooked and that takeout containers are observably clean and new, with both receiving a 296 or 73.4% agreement rate. However, this does not ensure the cleanliness of the containers as there are factors to consider such as if it is sealed, sanitized, and disinfected. This indicates that the customers are generally confident and satisfied with the safety and sanitation of takeout foods.

Table 2. Respondents' Assessment on Food Safety and Sanitation Practices (Evident)

Statements	Frequency	Percentage
1. Foods may be taken to go.	315	78.2%
2. Food is adequately cooked.	296	73.4%
3. The takeout containers are observable, clean, and new.	296	73.4%
4. Utensils are given upon serving food.	295	73.2%
5. Food that is served looks appetizing and has no foul odor.	295	73.2%
6. Take outs are placed on reusable plastic containers.	266	66%
7. Clean trays are used when food is being served.	251	62.3%
8. The business provides napkin to customers if asked.	267	66.3%
9. Condiments or sauces are properly stored in a container (e.g., squeeze bottle).	266	65.8%
10. Cook / Server checks the food quality.	251	62.3%

The use of reusable plastic containers comes with an even lower agreement rate with only 266 or 66%. Although it is still a majority, this possibly indicates that some food stalls use single use containers which are put at a greater risk of contamination as opposed to reusable containers (Piser, 2024). Both the provision of utensils upon serving food and the appetizing presentation and odor of the food received a 295 or 73.2% evident response. This means that servers tend to notice the presentation and quality of the food before serving it. The lowest agreement percentage was for the cleanliness of trays when serving food and cook or server checks the food quality both with only 251 or 62.3%. This is contradictory with the statements number 4 and 5 which indicate either a real issue with tray cleanliness and lack of attentiveness of cooks and/or servers or a problem with the customer perception which may be addressed by further improving service. The business also provides napkins to the customers if asked, with a high agreement rate of 267 or 66.3%. Lastly, as observed by the respondents, condiments or sauces are properly stored in a container with 266 or 65.8% agreement rate. Based on the overall results, the general public sees a positive perception of the food safety and sanitation practices of the food stalls.

The next table shows the assessment of the customer-respondents regarding food safety and sanitation practices that are not evident. Hand sanitizer is not available in the facility as observed by 200 or 49.6% of the respondents which greatly poses a risk to the customer's health; in study by Annegowda et al. (2021) it is stated that before eating, it is advisable to clean hands with soap and water or if not with alcohol-based sanitizers since hand sanitizers are an effective protection against pathogens that may cause diseases. In the second statement, 198 or 49.1% of the respondents stated that the food stalls do not provide information about ingredients and food allergies. Handwashing areas are also not observed in the establishment according to 191 or 47.4% participants of the study.

Table 3. Respondents' Assessment on Food Safety and Sanitation Practices (Not Evident)

Statements	Frequency	Percentage
1. Hand sanitizers are available in the facility.	200	49.6%
2. The food stall provides information about ingredients and food allergies.	198	49.1%
3. Faucet and soap are available for hand washing.	191	47.4%
4. The food stalls adjust recipes and food handling practices for customers with food allergies.	184	45.7%
5. The food allergies of customers are taken into consideration when planning meals at food sites.	181	44.9%
6. Toilets and urinals are well-maintained and clean.	143	35.5%
7. Trash bins are available and not full.	167	41.4%
8. The floor is clean in the establishment.	171	42.4%
9. The overall appearance of the establishment is well-maintained.	147	36.5%
10. Walls around the establishment are clean.	175	43.4%
11. Insectors / Insect and pest repellents are seen in the establishment.	169	41.9%

One hundred and eighty-four (184) or 45.7% of the respondents observed that food stalls do not adjust food recipes and food handling practices for customers with food allergies. The food allergies of customers are not taken into consideration according to 181 or 44.9% respondents. As observed by 143 or 35.5% of the respondents, toilets and urinals in the establishment are not well maintained and cleaned. Trash bins are not available according to 167 or 41.4% respondents which can affect waste management. This is another prevalent issue which is also in a research study by Solon (2022) wherein the majority of street food vendors experience difficulty with proper waste disposal. This difficulty arises from inadequately designed vending locations and a lack of crucial services, particularly designated waste bins. The floor of the establishments is not clean as stated by 171 or 42.4% of the respondents. One hundred and forty-seven (147) or 36.5% of the respondents observed that the overall appearance of the establishment is not well maintained, which may affect customer satisfaction greatly. In relation, a study by Taştan and Soylu (2022) stated that customer satisfaction is achieved by several factors including the cleanliness of a restaurant. Walls around the establishment are not clean according to 175 or 43.4% of the respondents. Lastly, insect and pest repellents are not observed in the establishment by 169 or 41.9% of the respondents.

Table 4. Experimental Results

Tumbongan Stall Soup Samples	E. coli count
Tumbongan Stall A	<3.0
Tumbongan Stall B	<3.0
Tumbongan Stall C	<3.0

Three samples on different *Tumbongan* stalls in Manila are collected for laboratory testing using FDA BAM - 4 2020 (MPN Method) to determine if the said soup contains *E. coli* that exceeds the minimum count (<3.0) for safety consumption. Results showed that all samples contain less than 3 (<3.0) counts of *E. coli* which is safe for consumption and has low-level risk of contamination. This is to guarantee safe and quality food for customers, enhance reputation and health safety compliance of the *Tumbongan* stalls.

Table 5. Cooking / Preparation

Statements	Evident	Not Evident	No Sufficient Evidence
1. Employees avoid direct body contact in cooking / preparing the food.	235	146	22
2. Cook / Server checks the food quality before serving it.	251	119	33
3. Food stalls serves ready-to-eat food instead of cooking the food upon ordering.	218	142	43
4. Food stall serves raw meat.	134	169	100
5. Food is adequately cooked.	296	79	28
6. Food that is served looks appetizing and has no foul odor.	295	80	28
7. Foods are prepared in a clean area.	227	137	39
8. Food utensils and equipment used in cooking are clean.	239	115	49
9. The food station that is visible to the customer is clean and tidy.	243	129	31

Results on cooking / preparation showed that 58.3% of the respondents noticed that the employees of the selected *Tumbongan* stalls are wearing aprons and plastic gloves while preparing food to avoid physical contact that could possibly cause contamination to the food according to Kanwal (2023). A study conducted by Kanwal (2023) stated that food contamination resulted from poor hygiene among food vendors. These vendors lacked awareness of proper food safety practices. Food presentation plays an important role in dining for it activates the appetite of the consumer yet, Moscare-Balanquit and Dolon-Sanoria (2021) stated that customers lack knowledge on determining the foods doneness and they rely on appearance and taste but 73.2% of the respondents agreed that the food served in the selected *tumbongan* food stalls in Manila looks appetizing and served without foul odor. Food poisoning takes place because of improper cooking, and it allows bacteria to spread such as *Escherichia coli* and many more according to Nwagbara et al. (2018) and according to 73.4% of the respondents who already tried the *tumbong* soup, the food served is adequately cooked in the right temperature.

As shown on the next table, 55% of respondents observed proper cleaning and washing of plates, bowls, and cups used in *tumbong* soup, with the dishwashing station using fresh soap, but consumers were unable to observe the sanitation process used by the *Tumbongan* stalls to properly sanitize the dishes. The importance of cleanliness and availability of wiping cloth and utensils in food service establishments, highlighting moderate consumer satisfaction with these features are the key points of the study of Lim et al. (2013).

Table 6. Cleanliness / Hygiene

Statements	Evident	Not Evident	No Sufficient Evidence
1. The staff or residence are observed to be washing their hands properly when preparing and serving food.	176	147	80
2. Hand sanitizers are available in the facility.	128	200	75
3. Food preparation areas are cleaned with sanitizing cleaner.	178	157	68
4. Food preparation areas are also sanitized with food-grade cleaning agents.	180	154	69
5. Sponges and/or dishcloths used to wipe up liquid from the preparation area are clean.	178	143	82
6. The staff and residents wear clean clothing and apron when preparing food.	221	136	46
7. Kitchen staff wash their hands after handling raw meat.	150	161	92
8. Plates, bowls, and cups used in serving food are clean properly, washed, and sanitized.	225	125	53

The study found that 221 participants agreed that staff members wore clothes cleanly when preparing food, emphasizing the importance to keep food preparation areas clean to avoid food contamination. 54.8% of 403 respondents agree on clean clothing and aprons for food preparation, with some wearing additional kitchen attire like hairnets and facemasks, indicating most *tumbongan* stalls follow proper attire. Emphasizing the importance of clean clothing and food preparation areas for safety, the study of Elexson et al., (2023) reveals that 99% of food handlers in Kuching follow Food Hygiene Regulations of 2009. It also reveals low soap handwashing rates after handling raw meat, with different customs across countries. Similarly, kitchen staff at *tumbongan* stalls do not consistently practice handwashing, and it's unclear if soap is used in handwashing. Moreover, it is found that different countries had different handwashing customs, and some people thought that washing their hands with water was the same as handwashing with soap according to the study of Didier et al., (2021).

This next table discusses the receiving / service of the food stalls which states that 78.2% of respondents evidently stated that food they order on *tumbongan* stalls can be taken to go, this is because of the convenience aspect, busy lifestyles, time constraints, and limited seating capacity of the food stalls. This is in line with the study of Chua et al. (2020), wherein it is stated that it is particularly important that restaurateurs stay on top of consumer behavior in the restaurant industry – and this includes the consumer preference of taking their foods to go due to situational factors that affect their preferences in eating such as convenience, staff responsiveness, and overall atmosphere of the establishment. 73.4% of the respondents observed the cleanliness and newness of the takeout containers during their visit to *tumbongan* stalls. This observation was made visually by inspecting the containers themselves. However, this does not assure the safety of these containers as it is unknown whether the containers were new, sealed, sanitized, and/or disinfected.

Table 7. Receiving / Service

Statements	Evident	Not Evident	No Sufficient Evidence
1. Foods may be taken to go.	315	70	18
2. Takeouts are placed on reusable plastic containers.	266	99	38
3. The takeout containers are observably clean and new.	296	63	44
4. Utensils are given upon serving food.	295	70	38
5. The employees use gloves when handling and serving food to avoid cross-contamination.	185	158	60
6. The employees may be seen shouting or talking when serving food.	221	125	57
7. Clean trays are used when food is being served.	251	102	50
8. There are no foreign objects in the food served.	204	151	48
9. Servers do not touch food when serving it.	244	119	40
10. Employees / staff act professionally in serving the food.	243	127	33
11. Kitchen staff may be seen eating while preparing food for the customers.	170	157	76
12. The business provides napkin to customers if asked.	267	95	41
13. Condiments or sauces are properly stored in a container (e.g., squeeze bottle).	265	96	42

The study of Janssen et al. (2017) suggests that the strongest determinants of take-out food availability are density of food outlets and deprivation within the built environment. As consumers tend to prefer take-out foods, containers used in food preparation have a great impact within a business in terms of cleanliness. As observed by 185 of the respondents, employees of *Tumbongan* stalls do not use gloves when serving food to the customers which is considered as a risk of food contamination, this can be due to the certain reasons such as; employees prefer to wash and sanitize their hands rather than wearing gloves, lack of knowledge or compliance to regulations can also be a factor why employees tend to not wear gloves when serving food. Training in food hygiene that embodies the concept of risk should be implemented in restaurants to emphasize to food handlers the level of risk associated with their business. This includes awareness in food handling and proper hygienic routine among employees such as wearing protective gloves if they have any cuts, open wounds, or abrasions to avoid contamination and prevents the spreading of bacteria (Matriano et al., 2017). The survey respondents show a high agreement rate of 37.5% in not evident, indicating that there are cases of foreign objects being found in the food. Several factors such as the non-compliance in wearing proper attire, improper handling of the food, and poor establishment condition may be attributed to this problem.

This supports the study of Payne et al. (2023), where it states that foreign material contaminations can come from any point in the food production system from the field through processing, manufacturing, to transport to retail. Thus, it is critically important to ensure safe and quality food production to avoid putting consumers at risk.

Table 8. Allergens

Statements	Evident	Not Evident	No Sufficient Evidence
1. The food stall provides information about ingredients and food allergies.	123	198	82
2. The food stall adjusts recipes and food handling practices for customers with food allergies.	119	184	100
3. The food allergies of customers are taken into consideration when planning meals at the food site.	118	181	104

For food allergens, the survey questionnaires do not pertain to any specific allergy. Rather, the survey questionnaires refer to what the food stall exhibits. It is prevalent that food stalls do not provide information about ingredients and some kind of warning for food allergies in general as observed by 49.1% of the respondents. Insufficient labeling of food allergens has led to a rise in food allergy response cases in recent decades, according to Stankovich et al. (2023). Food stalls fail to provide allergen information since the personnel lack proper knowledge and training in food allergies. The employees are unable to disclose details regarding food allergies given that food stalls frequently lack standards and regulations to abide by. It is recommended that personnel have appropriate training to communicate effectively with the customers (Plechlo, 2019). Results also show that 184 or 45.7% of the respondents observed that the *Tumbongan* stalls do not take into consideration the food allergies of customers, as they do not adjust the recipes of the foods, they serve for customers that have food allergies. In connection with a study from McAdams et al., (2018), the common root of food allergy causes includes cross-contact and miscommunication between employees and customers. Adjusting the recipes in food stalls can vary due to the fixed ingredients in every menu. In addition, there is a significant chance of cross-contamination caused by the limited space of food stalls.

On the next table, according to 191 participants, or 47.4% of the total, handwashing facilities and soap are not always evident or available in the establishment. This demonstrates that there are times when handwashing facilities and soap are not available. Similarly, the study of Kumie and Zeru (2007) highlighted the sanitary deficiencies including poorly maintained kitchens, improperly managed facilities, absence of handwashing areas. This increases the risk of food contamination as the absence of handwashing areas means that the stalls are not adhering to proper hygiene practices. 147 or 36.5% of the respondents observed that establishments of *Tumbongan* stalls in Manila are not well maintained and clean to the appeal of customers. This concludes that staff of *Tumbongan* stalls lacks knowledge and training in maintaining the cleanliness of the establishment. Stalls do not have cleaning protocols such as cleaning schedules, regular maintenance and proper sanitation of establishment.

Table 9. Establishment Condition

Statements	Evident	Not Evident	No Sufficient Evidence
1. Toilets and urinals are well-maintained and clean.	101	143	159
2. Trash bins are available and not full.	141	167	95
3. The floor is clean in the establishment.	153	171	79
4. Faucet and soap are available for handwashing.	112	191	100
5. Walls around the establishment are clean.	144	175	84
6. Toilet paper is available in the comfort room.	95	167	141
7. Insecutors / Insect and pest repellents are seen in the establishment.	107	169	127
8. The tables and chairs are clean.	239	115	49
9. The food establishment has an unpleasant odor.	125	196	82
10. The overall appearance of the establishment is well-maintained.	210	147	46

The research by Tuzunkan and Albayrak (2016) highlights how customers' attitudes and behaviors are significantly shaped by the physical environment, leading customers to spend extended periods in a particular location, ultimately impacting their level of satisfaction. The food stalls showed no signs of unpleasant odor according to 48.6% of the respondents. This is likely due to the quick and frequent table service, especially right after the customers have finished eating; the staff immediately clears up the tables after the customers, which most likely mitigates any foul odors caused by food leftovers and crumbs. According to Kibret and Abera (2012), poorly managed food service establishments are sources of food borne illnesses and food handlers contribute to food borne illness outbreaks. Maintaining the overall appearance and condition of an establishment is critical to the business image because it determines the perception they aim to anchor to their consumers.

Conclusion

Sixty-eight percent of the 403 respondents of the survey were students, and 56.1% of the respondents were female. Affordability and accessibility were major factors for employed people (46.6%) who frequently visited *Tumbongan* stalls close to their places of employment or educational institutions. On average, they spent less than Php 500 on street food. Furthermore, 45.7% of respondents indicated that they were returning customers, indicating a fondness for eating at the food stalls in Tondo, Manila. Meanwhile, the assessment of respondents towards food safety and sanitation practices of selected *Tumbongan* stalls in Manila is excellent if based on the cooking and preparation, staff service and cleanliness and hygiene. However, conditions of the establishment of *Tumbongan* stalls exhibit poor sanitation management. Lastly, the experimental result of the study concludes that *tumbong* soup is safe for consumption as it exhibits less than 3 (<3.0) counts of *E. coli* content.

Recommendations

Local government units (LGUs) in Manila should raise awareness regarding food safety sanitation practices and enforce strict monitoring on food stalls with accordance to the Food Safety Act of 2013 (RA 10611) to improve food hygiene and cleanliness in the market. In addition to this, Solon (2022) stated that organizing a seminar or training related to sanitation and personal hygiene can contribute to continuously improving the standard of their food vending. LGUs and food establishment owners should join forces to achieve proactive sanitation management and to guarantee the cleanliness of street foods in the market. The Department of Health (DOH) should implement regular inspections of food stalls or establishments, to ensure that they strictly follow proper sanitation practices and cook food adequately so that it is safe for the customers to consume. Future researchers are recommended to use a comparative analysis approach instead of a descriptive analysis when examining *Tumbongan* stalls, as this permits a more systematic and objective assessment of several stalls, leading to a better understanding of their dynamics and possible areas for improvement.

According to Appinio Research (2023), comparative analysis allows for a structured comparison of various stalls based on specific criteria, enabling researchers to identify patterns, trends, and differences more effectively. Furthermore, according to Tanujaya et al., (2023), the comprehensive Likert scale is frequently used in qualitative approaches, addressing discussions regarding the application of statistical analysis, and allowing researchers to recognize comparisons across various groups or over time that offer insights into possible shifts in attitudes. However, it is crucial to guarantee that the scale items are direct and fairly divided between positive and negative remarks to prevent biased responses. Additionally, follow up testing of *Tumbongan* soups are advised in the comprehensive examination to acquire a more accurate set of results. It is always advantageous to run follow-up tests for an initial sample that was close to significance, given that the appropriate correction for multiple tests is applied (Tyler, 2022).

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